

THE ANALYTICAL AND NUMERICAL CHARACTERIZATION REGARDING INDENTATION OF COMPOSITE HONEYCOMB SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The honeycomb composite sandwich beam subjected to transverse indentation is investigated analytically and numerically. An analytical model with shear effect and nonlinear real elastic-plastic out-plane compressive behavior of the honeycomb are presented. The detailed plastic response of the honeycomb core subjected to compressive loading is obtained visually by finite element analysis. Then, the parameters related to honeycomb core used in the analytical model are characterized by uniaxial compression with finite element analysis. At the same time, finite element analysis of the beam subjected to static transverse indentation is compared with the developed analytical model by comparing the load-displacement response, which show quite good agreement. Considering different honeycomb materials and structures, the influence of key parameters, which reflect the plastic deformation characteristics and plateau stress, on the honeycomb composite sandwich beam subjected to static transverse indentation are discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite sandwich structures are widely used in engineering field due to high specific strength and stiffness, large energy absorbing and good damage tolerance. Composite honeycomb sandwich structure generally consists of thin upper-lower composite face sheets and a low density honeycomb core with light weight, as shown in Figure 1, which are widely used in secondary structures of aircraft, such as helicopter blades, radome, fairing, aileron, flap, rudder and tail, as well as ship's hull in field of transportation^[1,2]. Thus, considerable attention is attracted in the past decades.

Fig. 1. Construction of honeycomb sandwich structures

In serves, these structures are easily subjected to localized loadings, such as impacts of foreign objects, like birds, hailstones or gravel^[2-4]. Considering the inherent configuration of sandwich structures including thin face sheets and weak core, they are prone to be damaged by transverse indentation loads^[1,4,5]. The residual mechanical properties of sandwich structures are significantly influenced by upper face sheet deflection and core damages caused by transverse loading.

One key issue in this problem is the model for local mechanical behavior like indentation failure. Despite of costing experimental studies^[6-8] and numerical analyses^[2,6,8], several classical theoretical models for the quasi-static and dynamic loading process have been proposed^[9-11], with and without

considering the shearing effects. Taking the core as an elastic foundation, local loading on sandwich beams can be studied analytically, such as Winkler's model and Vlasov's model [2,6,9-16].

The most commonly model is Winkler's spring model[2,6,11-13,15] and models based on it: the core is treated as separate elastic springs in thickness directions as shown in Fig.2. Besides, another model named Vlasov's model takes the vertical shearing of the core into account. The foundation is considered to be elastic, isotropic and homogeneous.[2,8,10,12-14]

The aforementioned model treated core as perfect plastic material. However, the real-world material of crushing core might not present perfect constant stress plateau, especially for honeycomb [5,8,17], as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2 Sandwich beam resting on foundation.

Fig.3 The behavior of honeycomb subjected to out-of-plane compression.

This paper focus on the analytical and numerical modeling of composite honeycomb sandwich beam under transverse loadings. Firstly, the behavior of honeycomb core is modeled by Vlasov's model with an elastic-perfectly plastic and elastic-plastic foundation. Secondly, the response of the composite honeycomb sandwich beam before and after the crushing of the core is compared with the behavior given by the Winkler foundation with an elastic-perfectly plastic foundation and finite element method. Contrary to Winkler foundation, it indicates a quite good correlation for the indentation load-deflection curve and the crushed area of the honeycomb. Last, considering different honeycomb materials and structures, the influence of key parameters, which reflect the plastic deformation characteristics and plateau stress, on the honeycomb composite sandwich beam subjected to static transverse indentation are discussed.

2 PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

When subjected to local transverse indentation loading with lower face sheet supported by a rigid facing, the upper facesheet of sandwich beam appears local bending deformation and the core endures through thickness deformation, as shown in Fig.4(a). When the local deformation of the core exceeds the elastic ultimate, the core crushed locally near the loading point and upper facesheet, which will induce residual indentation of the beam and reduce the stiffness and strength apparently.

Fig.4 The sandwich beam under indentation: (a) Deformation pattern; (b) Analysis of the upper facesheet

To simplify the problem, the sandwich beam is separated into upper face sheet and core, in which core supports the upper face sheet, as shown in Fig.4(b). The general support force $r(x)$ is directly related to compressive deformation of core at the corresponding point. That's to say, the deflection of the upper face sheet is consistent with the deformation of core. Then the upper face sheet can be considered as a beam supported by a foundation, and the governing equation can be obtained by the minimum strain energy of the face sheet/core system.

$$D_f \frac{d^4 w(x)}{dx^4} + r(x) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where D_f is the rigidity of upper face sheet in unit width, E_s is the Young's modulus of the upper face sheet along longitudinal direction, I_s is the inertial moment of the upper face sheet, b is the width of the beam, $r(x)$ is the support force provided by the core along unit length. Considering the deflection of the upper face sheet is consistent with the deformation of the core along thickness direction, it is easy to given:

$$D_f \frac{d^4 w(x)}{dx^4} + \sigma(w) = 0 \quad (2)$$

where, $\sigma(w)$ is the real-world uniaxial compression behavior of the core, i.e. the relationship between deformation and compressive stress of the core.

The governing equation can be solved with the boundary condition at the loading point and the infinite free edge:

At the infinite free edge,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} w(x) = 0, \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} w'(x) = 0 \quad (3)$$

At the loading point,

$$w(0) = 0, \quad w'(0) = 0, \quad w'''(0) = \frac{P}{2D_f} \quad (4)$$

From the governing equation, it can be founded that the key factors are rigidity of upper face sheet in unit width and compression behavior of the core.

The typical compressive response of the honeycomb is shown in Fig. 3. The indentation behavior of sandwich structure is significantly influenced by the nonlinearity after peak load.

3 ANALYTICAL SOLUTION

3.1 Linear elastic response

Winkler foundation model is widely used to predict the local indentation of sandwich beams, where the core is presented as a system of independent and linear elastic springs. Contrary to Winkler's model, Vlasov's model considered the vertical shearing of the core, which takes the local stress gradient into consideration, by an elastic, isotropic and homogeneous foundation with two parameters, based on variational principle. Fig.5 shows the comparison of indentation load-displacement between the Winkler's model and Vlasov's model in elastic domain. As we can see, the result from Vlasov's model actually has larger slope, which means the shear effect of core material increases the resistance of core to facesheet.

Fig. 5. Comparison of indentation load-displacement

3.2 Elastic-plastic behavior

3.2.1 Winkler's model combined with core crushing

Fig. 6(a) shows the idealized elastic-perfectly plastic response of honeycomb under compression. Based on the elastic-perfectly plastic response of honeycomb core, the behavior of the sandwich structure can be divided into two stages: Stage I, elastic deformation stage of the core, as shown in Fig. 6(b) marked with A, belongs to the Winkler's model with elastic foundation; Stage II, elastic-plastic deformation stage of the core, the core near the loading site is damaged and the beam can be separated to elastic region apart from the loading site and perfectly plastic region near the loading site, as shown in Fig. 6(c) marked with B.

Fig. 6. Winkler's model based on elastic-perfectly plastic foundation: (a) Typical elastic-perfectly plastic behavior of the core; (b) Elastic deformation stage; (c) Elastic-plastic deformation stage

3.2.2 Modified Vlasov's model combined with core crushing

The vertical shearing of the core, which causes the local stress gradient in the core, results in local damage near the loading point of the core. Thus, it is better to take vertical shearing of the core into consideration, especially in the elastic stage response of the core before damage, as shown in Fig 7(a), in order to determine the damage critical point. As shown in Fig. 7(b), with the increasing of transverse loading, the elastic limit of the core is exceeded. Then, the core crushes and comes into the elastic-plastic deformation stage, and the vertical shearing of the crushed core is neglected.

Furthermore, the plastic response of the honeycomb core can be detailed obtained by finite element analysis, thus the governing equation can be further modified as:

$$x < l, \quad D_f \frac{d^4 w_p}{dx^4} - k_1 \frac{d^2 w_p}{dx^2} + r(w) = 0 \quad (5.1)$$

$$x \geq l, \quad D_f \frac{d^4 w_e}{dx^4} - k_1 \frac{d^2 w_e}{dx^2} + k_2 w_e = 0 \quad (5.2)$$

$$r(w) = \sigma_s + (\sigma_p - \sigma_s)(1 - e^{-\beta(w/t_c - \varepsilon_s)}) \quad (5.3)$$

Fig. 7 Modified Vlasov's model: (a) Elastic deformation stage; (b) Elastic-plastic deformation stage

Eq. (5) is the detailed governing equation with considering the shear effects in elastic deformation and the degradation stage of the core during deformation. Eqs. (5.1) and (5.3) represents the degradation stage of the core during deformation. Eq. (5.2) indicates the elastic deformation with consideration of shear effects. The parameters in Eq. (5.3), such as σ_s , σ_p , β and ε_s are directly related to the core material properties.

Actually, the shear stiffness of honeycomb core is degraded during the deformation. Therefore, a degradation factor related to deflection is proposed in the equation of crushing region

$$D_f \frac{d^4 w(x)}{dx^4} - \eta k_1 \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} + k_2 w(x) = 0 \quad (6)$$

where

$$\eta = \alpha_1 \frac{\sigma_s + (\sigma_p - \sigma_s)(1 - e^{-\alpha_2 \beta (w - w_s)})}{\sigma_s}$$

$$k_1 = G_{13} \int_{-t_c}^0 \phi^2 dz, \quad k_2 = \frac{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}{E_{11}E_{22}\Delta} \int_{-t_c}^0 \left(\frac{d\phi}{dz}\right)^2 dz$$

$$\phi(z) = \frac{\sinh[\gamma(1 - z/t_c)]}{\sinh(\gamma)}, \quad \gamma^2 = t_c^2 \frac{G_{13} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{dw}{dx}\right)^2 dx}{\frac{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}{E_{11}E_{22}\Delta} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} w^2 dx}$$

4. COMPARISON WITH FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

The honeycomb sandwich structure subjected to static indentation loading is simulated with finite element method. Then the results are compared with those obtained by the newly developed model in section 3.2.

The geometry configuration of the honeycomb sandwich structure is shown in Fig. 8. The detailed structures of honeycomb core is considered. The honeycomb core is modeled with S4R shell element. Young's modulus of the cell walls is 3.5GPa.

Fig. 8 The FEM model of honeycomb sandwich beam

A displacement controlled loading condition is used to the middle in longitudinal direction along the whole width to simulate the indentation condition. The bottom of the honeycomb sandwich beam is rigidly constrained to avoid global bending deformation, which can be easily observed during three points bending loading condition.

Fig. 9 shows the indentation load-displacement response of the honeycomb sandwich beam from both finite element analysis and the newly developed present model in section 3.2. It indicated that it can reflect the response of the honeycomb sandwich beam subjected to indentation.

With the increasing of the indentation displacement, the honeycomb sandwich structure response changes from elastic to plastic. The critical load, a maximum load during the linear load-displacement response, is over 1000N obtained from finite element analysis. The predicted value is slightly overestimated compared with that obtained from finite element analysis. With the increasing of indentation loading after critical load, the response of the honeycomb beam appears nonlinear because of the core crushing.

Fig. 9 Indentation load-displacement

5. PARAMETER STUDY

In fact, material parameters of different honeycomb types and materials are not identical. For out-of-plane compression, the nonlinearity mentioned above of honeycomb is different as well. For instance, with the same type, aluminum honeycomb has more plastic deformation compared to paper honeycomb, which corresponding to small value of β . The parameter σ_p represent the plateau stress of honeycomb material, which indicates the bear capacity after plastic deformation and changes with the material and cell type. These difference can be present through different parameters in the $r(w)$, in Eq.(5.3):

The parameter β and σ_p will be studied in this section. The out-of-plane compression curve with different β and σ_p are in Fig.10.

Fig. 10 Out-of-plane compression curve with different parameters

5.1 Influence of β

The parameter β represents the plastic deformation of honeycomb material. The larger β gives a gently decline to plateau force. The indentation results with different parameter β is shown in Fig. 11.

The force after elastic region decrease with the increasing of parameter β . When the honeycomb out-of-plane compressive stress decrease, the indentation force does not decrease immediately, which depends on the sharp decreasing of the curve. If the crushing domain of the curve is not steep, the indentation force will not decrease after the crushing initiation. On the contrary, the indentation force has a load drop after the elastic deformation.

Fig. 11 Indentation load-displacement with parameter β

5.2 Influence of plateau stress

The parameter σ_p represent the plateau stress of honeycomb material. The indentation results with different parameter σ_p is shown in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12 Indentation load-displacement with parameter σ_p

The force after elastic region increase with the increasing of plateau stress. the indentation force will not decrease after the crushing initiation with lower plateau stress. Similar with the parameter beta, if the compressive stress is large enough, the indentation force has no load drop during the loading process.

6 CONCLUSION

Several foundation model have been developed to describe the indentation behavior of the sandwich beam, such as Winkler's elastic and elastic-perfectly plastic foundation and Vlasov's elastic and elastic-perfectly plastic foundation, which shown their ability to solve the problems.

The vertical shearing of the core, which causes the local stress gradient in the core, results in local damage near the loading point of the core. Thus, it is better to take account of out-of-plane shearing effect of the core both in the elastic and collapse stage response of the core. Furthermore, the detailed plastic response of the honeycomb core obtained by finite element analysis are used to modify the existing models. Thus, in this paper,

1) Considering the shear effects of the honeycomb, the modified Vlasov's model considering shear effect in both elastic and crush region is used to predict the response of honeycomb sandwich beam subjected to indentation.

2) An analytical model with the real nonlinear elastic-plastic plastic compressive behavior of the honeycomb are presented. The detailed plastic response of the honeycomb core subjected to compressive loading can be visually obtained by finite element analysis. Then, the load-displacement response of

beam subjected to static indentation is analyzed by the developed analytical model, which is compared with those from finite element analysis, and shows quite good agreement.

3) It can be noted that basic factors of the geometry parameters, such as width of the beam, thickness of the upper face sheet might influence the indentation behavior. And the cell size of honeycomb core affecting the material properties, such as Young's modulus and plateau stress of the honeycomb core under compression can results in different indentation for sandwich structures.

4) Considering different honeycomb materials and structures, the key factors that have great influence on the honeycomb composite sandwich beam subjected to static indentation, are β and σ_p , which reflect the plastic deformation and plateau stress respectively.

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